

Validity of the Vietnamese Version of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index

To Minh Ngoc^{1,2*}, Nguyen Do Nguyen¹, Phung Khanh Lam², Tran Thi Xuan Lan¹ and Nguyen Xuan Bich Huyen³

¹Ho Chi Minh city University of Medical and Pharmacy, Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam

²Leafshield Group of Researchers, Project Development Department, Vietnam Medical Assistant Program, Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam

³Community Health Care Center, Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam

Abstract

As a neurological problem, insomnia or any other sleep disorder were always hardly noticed at the very beginning and even harder to evaluate its consequences at the end. It is essential to identify a valid sleep quality measurement that can be administered widely in the community in order to assist effectively the clinicians on the evaluation of sleep complaints. This study aimed to examine the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) on Vietnamese patients with sleep disorders as a general measure of sleep quality. After the forward-backward translation, 122 subjects who had sleep complaints were recruited to answer the PSQI, 36 of them filled in the PSQI again 2 weeks later and 86 of them slept over night at the Clinic for a polysomnography. The results showed that overall the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.789, indicating a good internal consistency. Correlation coefficient was 0.77. Test-retest reliability coefficient was 0.79. Limit of agreement analysis showed an oscillation range from -4.51 to 5.45 of PSQI score, the within-subject coefficient of variation showed that 95% measurements had 27.25% difference compared to the mean score. At cut-off, the sensitivity and specificity were 87.76% and 75%, respectively, with the area under the curve was 0.7583. The present findings support that the Vietnamese Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index is a reliable tool and can be used for sleep disorder patient or community screening.

Keywords: Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, sleep disorders, sleep quality, validation, Vietnamese version

1. Introduction

Bad sleep can be caused by various factors, either psychiatric or medical conditions. Previous studies also showed chronic diseases such as renal and cardiology problems [1-3] can lead to sleep-related illness and low quality of life. As a neurological problem, sleep disorder was always hardly noticed at the very beginning and even harder to evaluate its consequences at the end. The current gold standard to support clinician diagnosis of sleep illness is polysomnography (PSG) [4]. Nevertheless it's a limited approach when it comes to large-sample studies or community screening. Moreover, the PSG test is not easily affordable for most of ordinary people in low and middle in-

come countries (LMIC), therefore it is essential to identify a valid sleep quality measurement that can be administered widely on the community in order to assist effectively the clinicians on sleep complaint evaluation. There are several self-report questionnaires, which are alternative methods to measure sleep quality, have been developed such as Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) [5], Basic Nordic Sleep Questionnaire (BNSQ) [6], Sleep Disorders Questionnaire (SDQ) [7], and Sleep Quality Scale (SQS) [8]. Among those, ESS is the shortest scale but only for daily sleep disorder, BNSQ is not so popular and SDQ is too long with the total of 175 questions, SQS has just developed from 2006 and hasn't been validated in many languages yet.

Corresponding author: To Minh Ngoc
Head of Project Development Department, Vietnam Medical Assistant Program
Tel: +84.908088219
Email: ngoc.to@vnmap.org
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The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was developed in 1989 with high reliability on sleep illness subjects. A global PSQI score more than 5 indicated a person having bad quality sleep with sensibility and specificity obtained 98.7% and 84.4%, respectively [9]. It consists of 7 components, 3 factors and 19 sub-items; designed for self-answered and aimed to evaluate a person's sleep quality within the last month [10]. Many versions of PSQI are translated and validated in Italian, Hebrew, Korean, Japanese, Chinese, Persian, Greek, Nigerian, and Spanish [3, 9-23].

In Vietnam, the data of insomnia or sleep disorder was evaluated indirectly and basically through out the psychiatric surveys. Besides, the PSQI has been used in several studies to assess sleep quality on different group of patients without a standard validation progress [3, 9, 11, 12, 14, 18-20, 22-24]. Thus, the study was conducted to assess the validity and reliability of the Vietnamese version Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index in Vietnamese community.

2. Methods

In this particular study, bi-lingual translation validation was conducted initially before any other study procedure. The translation revision was discussed by all team members and final reports were submitted to MAPI TRUST organization for Vietnamese translation's version documented.

A cross-sectional study was designed, in which the participants were approached to participate at the Sleep Clinics, Community Health Care Centre in Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam. A re-test after 2 weeks was performed for reliability analysis. The sample size was calculated based on specific objective's requirement, using Structural equation modeling - SEM on Statistica 10 software. As a combination result from overall objectives, this particular study

needed at least 119 participants in total. Data was collected by self-answered questionnaire; completed forms were immediately checked and signed for completion by an research assistant. Subjects were also examined and diagnosed based on DSM-IV criteria for Dys-somnias and Parasomnias. The investigators documented clinical results on patient medical record file attached with polysomnography results (only for subjects with physician indication).

All data were analyzed by R software. Social and anthropological features were described by mean and standard deviation value to quantitative variables with normal distribution, by median and quartile to quantitative variables without normal distribution, by frequent and proportion to qualitative variables. Reliability was described by mean and standard deviation to total mark of the scale, other results were analyzed including Cronbach's alpha, correlation coefficient, reliability coefficient, ROC curve.

All participants were collected informed consent before any study procedures. The study was conducted with ethical committee approval from the faculty of Public Health, Ho Chi Minh city University of Medical and Pharmacy and from the Ho Chi Minh city Scientific and Technology Department.

3. Results

Demographic information: A total of 122 subjects were enrolled with average age of 43-year-old, in which 86 subjects participated for one time only and 36 subjects participated for the re-test after 2 weeks (Table.1). 63 female (51.64%) and 59 male (48.36%) were distributed significantly different in each range (Fisher test $p = 0.02$), mainly female subjects were in the age of 20 and middle-age. For PSG test there were 65 subjects spent one night at the clinics and diagnosed based on the DSM-IV criteria.

Table 1. Age range demographic (n=122)

Age range	n	%
Median (min-max)	43 (20 - 76)	
< 30	22	18.0
30 - 39	30	24.6
40 - 49	29	23.8
50 - 59	27	22.1
≥ 60	14	11.5
Total	122	100.0

Global PSQI total score: Sleep quality score was not distributed normally (mean 9.2 and standard deviation 5.13), however Skewness analysis indicated that this data had an approximate normal distribution (skewness=0.36, median=9, quarterly percentile=5-12). The total score of sleep quality was 13.27 ± 3.92 in patient group, 4.08 ± 2.15 in control group (Table 2).

Internal consistency: The Barlette test considered the hypothesis H_0 : the correlation between the observed variables equal to 0 in condition $\chi^2 = 755.43$ and $p < 0.001$; KMO = 0.71; showed that the condition for factor analysis is achieved. General Cronbach's alpha was 0.789 indicating a good internal consistency, nonetheless this is still in low average compared to other versions (range 0.72 to 0.89).

Table 2. Sleep quality score

The components (#with only 1 subcomponent)	Positive result group - median	Negative result group - median	Cronbach's alpha
Factor 1: Sleep efficiency	1	1	0.730
Sleep duration [#]	1	1	-
Sleep efficiency	1	1	0.439
Factor 2: Sleep quality	0	0	0.763
Hypnotic medication use [#]	1	1	-
Sleep latency	0	0	0.839
Subjective sleep quality [#]	1	1	-
Factor 3: Daily disturbances	1	1	0.693
Sleep disturbance	1	1	0.647
Daytime dysfunction	1	1	0.835
Global PSQI score (M ±SD)	13.27 ± 3.92	4.08 ± 2.15	-

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) model: The minimum sample size per each variable was 5 while this data obtained 6 per each variable,

which is the condition for correlation reveal in the model. The correlation coefficient between factors obtained 53 with $p < 0.001$.

Fig.1. Confirmatory factor analysis model

C: Components of PSQI (from C1 to C7); F: Factors of PSQI (from F1 to F3)
 Gam: Factor loading for each component; Theta: Factor loading between each factor and components
 Sigma: Factor loading between scale's factors

Akaike information criterion (AIC) obtained 69 was low, showing that the model was in ultimate adjudication. Bayesian information criterion (BIC) obtained -20 showed the model meet only 1 criteria either "good parameter" or model complexity". The PSQI scale consisted of only 7 components which can be considered as a low level of complexity, consequently the eligible criteria likely was the "good parameter".

Reliability of PSQI scale

R obtained 0.79 with var (t) = 12.73 and var (e) = 3.35 showed an average reliability only if PSQI score followed the standard distribution. Nevertheless, the data distribution did not achieve the condition which pulls the trigger for need of other assessment of reliability for this version. The findings showed 95% measurements had significant difference score of 3.59 in comparison to that particular subject's previous score. The within-subject coefficient of variation obtained 27.25%.

Table 3. Initial assessment by R coefficient calculation

Mean	Variance	$\sum_{i=1}^n \text{BSS} (\chi^2 - 6.68) \chi^2$	BMS = BSS / N	WSS = d	WMS = WSS / N
6.68	3.35	1037.15	28.81	120.5	3.35
$\frac{s_r^2}{k} = (BMS - WMS) / k$		$\frac{s_e^2}{k} = WMS$	K = no measurement	R = $s_r^2 / (s_r^2 + s_e^2)$	
12.73		3.35	2	0.79	

Table 4. Alternative assessment for reliability with SEM and wCV calculation

	Variations mean	Standard error of measurement (SEM)	1.96 x SEM	Within-subject coefficient of variation (wCV)
Score	3.35	1.82	3.59	27.25%

Sensitivity and specificity: The receiver operating curve (ROC) calculation obtained 0.7583 in line with the credit range (from 0.7 to 0.8).

At cut-off point at 5, the Vietnamese version of PSQI got a sensitivity of 87.76% and a specificity of 75%; with the LR+ equal to 3.51.

Fig.2. ROC curve of multiple cut-off points

Table 5. Sleep quality at cut-point of 5

Diagnosis	PSQI score		Total
	+	-	
+	43	6	49
-	4	12	16
Total	47	18	65

KAPPA at cut-point PSQI of 5: Diagnosis based on the DSM-IV and PSQI score were put in 2x2 table, showed 43 real positive cases and 12 real negative cases in total 65 subjects performed the PSG test.

4. Discussion

Of all 122 enrolled subjects, 70.5% had age data concentrated in a certain cluster from 30- to 50-year-old. The total score of sleep quality was significantly different between the studied and the control group, the score ranges were quite similar with the original version [9] (13.27 vs. 11.09 and 4.08 vs. 2.67).

The study population’s condition qualified for factor analysis with general Cronbach’s alpha was 0.789 indicating a good internal consistency. Similar versions with the Vietnamese version are Japanese (0.77), Hebrew (0.76);

the higher scores are Korean, Chinese, Italian and the original (0.84 – 0.835 – 0.825 – 0.82, respectively) [3, 9, 12, 14, 15, 17, 19, 20, 22]. The test-retest measurement used wCV coefficient of variation instead of R coefficient calculation. The result of 27.25% wCV means that there is a 95% probability the measurements will fluctuate around 27.25% compared to the average value of all measurements. The oscillation between test and re-test scores showed the Vietnamese version have a high reliability. With similar metrics, Chinese and Greek’s version also obtained 0.85 and 0.82, respectively.

ROC showed the parameters concentration on the north-western part of the map, which is a good value with high sensitivity and low false positive rate. At cut-off point of 5, the Vietnamese version of PSQI showed high sensitivity, LR+ 3.51 means when a person have a positive PSQI result, the probability of that

person diagnosed with sleep illness will be 3.51 times higher than the negative one. Other versions chose the cut-off point of 5 are Japanese, Chinese, Persian and Nigeria. Nonetheless, the most found similar to Vietnamese version is the Japanese [15] version, with sensitivity of 75.7% and specificity of 86.6% among the sleepless subjects, 80-86.6% among the depression subjects, 83.3% and 86.6% among the anxiety subjects and 83.3%-86.6% among the schizophrenia subjects. KAPPA at this cut-off point obtained 60.23% showed the agreement between the clinician diagnoses (supported by PSG result) with the PSQI scores lined in the higher average range.

5. Conclusions

This present findings support that the Vietnamese Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index is a reliable tool and can be used for sleep disorder patient evaluation or community screening.

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